

BRANKA MEIC SALIE, MA*

REASONABLE ACCOMMODATION - A PRECONDITION FOR EQUALITY OF PERSONS WITH DISABILITIES ON THE LABOUR MARKET

Abstract:

The UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) makes reasonable accommodation central to realising equal opportunities for persons with disabilities in all areas of life, work and employment in particular. This principle has been incorporated into Croatian legislation via the EU Directive 2000/78 on equal treatment in employment and occupation.

While protecting, monitoring and promoting the rights of persons with disabilities the Disability Ombudsman's Office finds that there is a lack of application of the principle in practice in particular in combating discrimination on the grounds of disability through litigation.

To facilitate development of the practice in this area the article presents a case from the practice of the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) (Cases C-335/11 and C-337/11 Ring and Skouboe Werge). In this judgment from 2013 the CJEU defines disability in line with the CRPD, explains the position of the CRPD in the EU legal system and interprets reasonable accommodation.

Key words: *reasonable accommodation, disability ombudsman, disability based discrimination at work, part time work, disproportionate burden*

* Advisor of disability ombudswoman, Disability Ombudsman's Office, Croatia, E-mail: branka.meic@posi.hr

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To begin with I must say that my educational background is not in law. However, I believe the insights I gained during seven years of working at the Disability Ombudsman’s office as the advisor for international cooperation through following the theory and practice of discrimination on the ground of disability in EU member states and elsewhere, as well as analysing policy and complaints handled by the Disability Ombudsman might be useful for those who can contribute to making anti-discrimination legislation an effective tool in combating widespread inequality and unfavourable treatment of persons with disabilities in practice.

I will start by briefly presenting the Disability Ombudsman’s Office and its three fold mandate. I will share some of my observations regarding the state of play on the implementation of anti-discrimination legislation in Croatia drawing on examples from the practice of the Office. Since the United Nations adopted its youngest human rights treaty in 2006, the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD), nothing pertaining to persons with disabilities can be discussed without taking into consideration its provisions. Therefore I will try to explain why this international legal document makes reasonable accommodation central to realising equal opportunities for persons with disabilities in all areas of life, work and employment in particular and how it defines disability.

As one of my conclusions regarding the implementation of anti-discrimination legislation on the grounds of disability is the need for developing a body of court practice and strategic litigation, I will discuss a case from the practice of the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) which defines disability in line with the CRPD, explains the position of the CRPD in the EU legal system and interprets reasonable accommodation to help toward developing the practice.

The Disability Ombudsman’s Office of the Republic of Croatia was established on 1 July 2008 as an independent state institution reporting to Parliament. In May that year the UN CRPD ratified by Croatia entered into force and establishing a specialised body for protection, promotion and monitoring of the rights of persons with disabilities was one of the measures in the National Plan for Equalisation of Opportunities for Persons with Disabilities from 2007-2015 in the area of strengthening their legal protection. The office has a broad mandate which involves the functions of an **ombudsman’s** office handling complaints in the area of maladministration, a **human rights institution** that promotes disability rights as human rights and monitors legislation and its implementation as well as an **equality body** mandated with implementing the Anti-discrimination Act in the area of disability.

The mandate of the Disability Ombudsman’s Office entails:

- dealing with complaints of persons with disabilities and children with developmental difficulties on all matters and in all areas towards both government agencies and private entities

- monitoring compliance of legislation with legally binding international documents in the field of protection of rights of persons with disabilities primarily the UN CRPD. In that respect the Office to the best of its abilities fulfils the role of an independent body for the protection, promotion and monitoring of the CRPD according to the Article 33 (2) of the CRPD
- proposing amendments to legislation pertaining to the rights of persons with disabilities

The number of complaints to the disability ombudsman alleging discrimination has been steadily increasing from 25 in 2011 to 97 in 2015. There are very few cases appearing in court involving discrimination on the grounds of disability in Croatia and the general level of awareness of discrimination, in particular in the form of denial of reasonable accommodation, is very low. Monitoring of the court practice is made further difficult if not impossible due to the very poor practice of courts to make their judgments available.

The Disability Ombudswoman employs so called soft law measures in fighting discrimination: issuing recommendations and warnings and requesting reports on the measures undertaken to remove discriminatory practices. This can provide efficient and timely relief through a kind of informal mediation which the Office frequently carries out in particular in the area of access to education. Since some of the reasons why persons with disabilities despite being faced with widespread discrimination in all areas of life do not resort to the courts are the cost and duration of court proceedings this is for them often a preferable way of seeking redress. The Disability Ombudsman cannot represent complainants in a court of law but can intervene in the proceedings on behalf of the complainant. The Office could also initiate class actions but its budget does not contain allocations for potential court cases.

The Anti-discrimination Act in Croatia entered into force on 1 January 2009. It prohibited discrimination on 18 grounds including disability. It specifically listed denial of reasonable accommodation to persons with disabilities as a form of discrimination. Denial of reasonable accommodation is deemed to be failure to enable persons with disabilities to use publicly available resources, take part in public and social life, access work place and adequate working conditions through adjustments of infrastructure and space, use of equipment and in other ways which are not a disproportionate burden for anyone who is obliged to provide these conditions.¹

The Anti-discrimination act in its provisions prohibits discrimination in almost all areas of life: work and working conditions, employment, access to vocational training and further education, education at all levels, science, sports, social security (including areas of social care, pension and health insurance and insurance in cases of unemployment), health care, justice and administration, housing, public information and media, access to

¹ Zakon o suzbijanju diskriminacije, *eng.* Anti-discrimination Act, (Official Gazette 85/08, 112/12), art. 8

and provision of goods and services, membership and conducting affairs in trade unions, non-governmental organizations, political parties or other organizations, taking part in cultural and artistic activities.²

At the moment there are four ombudsman offices in Croatia: People's, Children's Ombudsman, Gender Equality Ombudsman and Disability Ombudsman.

In December 2014 a number of stakeholders gathered to mark the 15th anniversary of the entering into force of the Anti-discrimination Act in Croatia. The summary of the discussion could be that the grieved parties on all grounds rarely resort to the Anti-discrimination Act as a tool to address their grievances, lawyers seem to be uncertain in the implementation of the provisions which have a number of features alien to the continental law system and one of the present judges admitted to discrimination cases being a hot potato for judges. The general feeling expressed by the members of the academia, civil society, judiciary and lawyers was that of disappointment and frustration that the Act had not really come to life and, as is customary, there was a lot of blame passing. But the fact is that the prohibition of discrimination in employment entered into legislation in the United States back in 1965. The concept of reasonable accommodation was first introduced in the Americans with Disabilities Act, a federal civil rights law that was passed in 1990 and went into effect beginning in 1992. It required employers to provide reasonable accommodation for employees with disabilities. Compared to such a long history of combating discrimination in general and discrimination on the ground of disability in particular it is hardly surprising that we are still experiencing teething difficulties.

That standard was adopted by the European Union through the Council Directive 2000/78/EC on Equal treatment in employment and occupation. During the pre-accession negotiations the Directive was transposed into Croatian legislation by adoption of the Anti-discrimination act (OG, 85/08, 112/12).

In 2008 Croatia ratified the UN Convention on the rights of persons with disabilities (UN CRPD). The UN CRPD is the first international treaty signed by a union of states and also the first international treaty that the EU has become a party to in 2009.

Who are persons with disabilities and why is the concept of reasonable accommodation important for exercising their right to work?

Under Article 1 of the UN Convention *persons with disabilities include those who have long-term physical, mental, intellectual or sensory impairments which in interaction with various barriers may hinder their full and effective participation in society on an equal basis with others.*³ (underlined by the author).

² Zakon o suzbijanju diskriminacije, *eng.* Anti-discrimination Act, (Official Gazette, 85/08, 112/12), art. 4 (2)

³ *UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities*, Art. 1, <http://www.un.org/disabilities/convention/conventionfull.shtml>, (accessed 18 April 2016).

Impairment including	physical	Interaction with BARRIERS	= DISABILITY (hindrance to participation)
	sensory		
	intellectual		
	mental (psychosocial)		

What is important to note about this non-definition of disability is that it does not provide an exhaustive list of impairments that might lead to disability. Also, it does not equate impairment with disability. The definition of disability when fighting discrimination will in particular be wider than it is defined in for instance social policy or in other areas through which various entitlements are provided. This is due to the fact that the purpose of anti-discrimination provisions is to promote inclusion and therefore everyone who encounters problems in participating in the labour market due to impairment or a health condition is considered to be a person with disability although they do not have to be considered a person with disability by other systems or in the general sense of that word as we are used to it. All these considerations will prove relevant in the joint cases C-335/11 and C-337/11 Ring and Skouboe Werge before the Court of Justice of the European Union which we will look into later.

The second important feature of this non-definition makes a clear shift from the so called medical model of disability in which disability was equated with a person's impairment and this impairment was seen as a natural limitation of a person's rights. The UN CRPD defines disability as an interaction between an impairment and barriers in the society. In that way it is the society that turns an impairment a person has into an inability to participate in different areas of life. This at the same time means that the society can and has an obligation to remove obstacles to participation. In a very simple illustration of that concept, stairs at the entrance into a building will hinder participation of a wheelchair user in any activities taking place in that building. If stairs are replaced by a universally designed entrance or supplemented with a ramp, the mobility impairment will not hinder participation of a wheelchair user. The focus of any disability assessment should thus be moved from limitations that impairments pose and instead look at the remaining capabilities and potentials of the person while proposing support interventions that would mitigate those limitations.

Barriers to participation of persons with disabilities can be prevented by designing products and services in line with the principles of universal design which takes into account the needs of as broad as possible a spectrum of potential users and not just an average user. In case of the existing buildings or services barriers are removed by means of reasonable accommodation.

Under the fourth indent of Article 2 of the Convention, "*Reasonable accommodation*" means necessary and appropriate modification and adjustments not imposing a disproportionate or undue burden, where needed in a particular case, to ensure to persons with

*disabilities the enjoyment or exercise on an equal basis with others of all human rights and fundamental freedoms.*⁴

Recitals 16 and 17 in the preamble to the EU directive on Equal Opportunities in employment 2000/78 explain the importance of reasonable accommodation for persons with disabilities and its limits.

(16) The provision of measures to accommodate the needs of disabled people at the workplace plays an important role in combating discrimination on grounds of disability.

*(17) This Directive does not require the recruitment, promotion, maintenance in employment or training of an individual who is not competent, capable and available to perform the essential functions of the post concerned or to undergo the relevant training, without prejudice to the obligation to provide reasonable accommodation for people with disabilities.*⁵

In practice determining whether a certain work task or practice which needs to be adjusted falls under the scope of essential function of the post will be a most frequent consideration. A person without the use of his or her hands at a managerial position may need assistance in the way of a typist who would put their interventions in writing. The essential function for that post will not be that of typing unlike for the post of typist who should actually be able to type. This does not mean that blind or deaf persons cannot be typists if the way in which they carry out the activity of typing is adjusted by enabling them to use a voice operated personal computer or a sign language translator. Such an approach enables a much wider number of persons with disabilities who were previously excluded from the labour market to exercise their right to work. It does not stop at saying: *we have nothing against employing persons with disabilities. On the contrary, we are more than willing to employ them but they cannot work.* The new model does not allow that impairment be seen as a natural limitation of their right to work but requires an employers to look into ways in which some characteristics of their environment or work processes can actually exclude differently abled workers. It also poses an obligation on employers to modify such practices to the extent which will not cause them an undue burden.

To sum up, we could say that denial of reasonable accommodation will lead to less favourable treatment of persons with disabilities, which is discrimination. On the other hand, providing reasonable accommodation will in a way neutralise impairment and enable a person with disability to participate in the labour market in line with their remaining capacities. Nowadays direct discrimination of persons with disabilities in work, employment and all other areas is very infrequent. Employers do not say that they have turned

⁴ UN *Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities*, Art. 1, <http://www.un.org/disabilities/convention/conventionfull.shtml>, (accessed 18 April 2016).

⁵ Council Directive 2000/78/EC of 27 November 2000 establishing a general framework for equal treatment in employment and occupation, Official Journal L 303 , 02/12/2000 P. 0016 - 0022

down a prospective candidate due to their disability. However, they might be tempted to include seemingly neutral provisions that would place persons with disabilities in an unfavourable position. A more frequent scenario is finding persons with disabilities unfit to work because they cannot perform all the functions of the job in a manner expected from an average employee. In other words, it is not taken into consideration whether a person with a disability is capable of performing essential functions of a job and whether adjustments that would not cause undue burden could be made to the manner in which tasks are carried out. In that way persons with disabilities are discriminated against by denial of reasonable accommodation and their impairment is seen as a natural limitation of their right to work in line with the old model of disability.

Impairment – reasonable accommodation = treated less favourably (discrimination)

Impairment + reasonable accommodation = participation in line with remaining capacities

The situation with applying the principle of reasonable accommodation in employment in Croatia can be illustrated by a complaint handled by the Disability Ombudsman's Office. A person with visual impairment applied for the post of a courtroom note taker. Fearing that his application would be rejected if the prospective employer found out about his disability, the client tried his best to hide it. However the disability was too severe not to be noticed. A part of the recruitment process consisted in testing the typing ability. The client was told that a person with such a severe visual impairment cannot be a courtroom note taker and that there was no point in him taking the test.

The ombudswoman issued a warning that such treatment is discriminatory and that the employer is obliged to ensure reasonable accommodation for testing. The client was then invited to take part in the test which required that a text is copied into a computer. The text was prepared in the augmented form but the client could not see the keys on the keyboard or the computer and could not save the text. It turned out he was using a screen reader during his education.

The prospective employer in this example failed to consider the adequacy of the adjustment. From the initial attitude which represented direct discrimination it became clear that the actual equalising of opportunities during the testing can be ensured only if reasonable accommodation is provided by way of using aids which the person is accustomed to using and which he would use to carry out working tasks in case he was given the job. The employer demonstrated a willingness to create equal opportunities but also lack of awareness of what adequate adjustment would be.

We at the Disability Ombudsman's Office see the abstract and succinct language of the Anti-discrimination Act and failure to incorporate discrimination provisions in more detail for instance in the Labour Act, by at least making a mention of reasonable accommoda-

tion as yet another factor that contributes to its poor implementation. This was noticed by the UN Committee on the rights of persons with disabilities during reviewing of the initial report on the implementation of the CRPD in Croatia. In its concluding observations the Committee noted that *there seems to be a lack of understanding of the meaning of reasonable accommodation and universal design in areas such as education, health, employment, built environment*⁶. Accordingly, it recommended to the Croatian government that *the concepts of reasonable accommodation and universal design are regulated beyond the context of the anti-discrimination act in areas such as education, health, transportation and building*.⁷

By way of comparison, the Disability Discrimination Act was enacted in Great Britain back in 1995 to be replaced by the Equality Act in 2010. It suffices to say that the Act has 251 pages. Among other things, it prescribes in detail measures required for combating discrimination and clearly identifies duty bearers.

Based on such long legislative tradition in combating disability based discrimination, a good practice has been developed in which employers actively seek input from applicants on whether they need any form of reasonable accommodation and what that accommodation should entail. The application form contains a following statement: *Please inform us if you need any form of reasonable accommodation due to disability so that we could ensure that you attend the interview or what you would like us to take into account when considering your application. Reasonable accommodation pertains to, among other things, sign language translators, modifying the time of the interview or securing an accessible room. If you have additional questions regarding your needs arising from disability, contact the human resources manager. That will not be discriminatory*.⁸ That kind of practice is only to be developed in Croatia and the example of a person with visual impairment demonstrates the urgency for its establishment.

One of the most striking facts in this case was a lack of communication on the part of person with disability who not only failed to communicate the need for accommodation but even tried to conceal his disability from the employer for fear that mentioning it would immediately disqualify him. Unfortunately, this fear was confirmed by the employer's subsequent conduct. Persons with disabilities who submit a complaint to the Disability Ombudsman's office are informed about the possibility to take their cases to court if the measures that the ombudswoman has at her disposal failed to stop discrimination. However, clients choose not to invest their limited financial, physical and emotional resources in legal battles with uncertain and potentially long and costly outcome. In a coun-

⁶ Concluding observations on the initial report of Croatia, (5), Committee on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, Thirteenth session, 25 March-17 April 2015

⁷ Concluding observations on the initial report of Croatia, (6)

⁸ L. Waddington, 'Primjer razumne prilagodbe i pozitivne akcije u Velikoj Britaniji, eng. An Example of reasonable accommodation and positive action in Great Britain' in *Priručnik za savjetnike na tržištu rada o metodama sveobuhvatnog promicanja zapošljavanja osoba s invaliditetom*, Zagreb, 2011, p. 316.

try which has no tradition of fighting discrimination people are not aware of their right to equal treatment especially when securing it seems like making (unreasonable) demands from the prospective employer. On the other hand, employers and other agents who have the obligation to provide reasonable accommodation are not aware of their obligation and see it as a matter of their goodwill or simply dismiss it. In that light any attempt at seeking reasonable accommodation is seen as seeking preferential treatment.

That is why litigation and court cases could be a particularly efficient awareness raising tool. Due to the lack of court practice in Croatia we find it very important to disseminate cases from the Court of Justice of the European Union which set precedents in dealing with disability discrimination.

CASES C-335/11 AND C-337/11 RING AND SKOUBOE WERGE

In the joint cases C335/11 and C337/11 Ring and Skouboe Werge v Dansk Arbejdsgiverforening from 2013 the national Danish court stayed the proceedings and asked the Court of Justice of the European Union to give interpretation of the EU law and to clarify the concept of disability.

In these two cases which were joined two women were dismissed following a period of sick leave. One woman suffered from constant lumbar pain which could not be treated and no prognosis could be made as regards the prospect of returning to full-time employment. The second woman sustained whiplash injuries as a consequence of a road traffic accident and was found unfit for work as an office assistant/management secretary. Similar to the first case, the doctor could not give an opinion on the duration of the unfitness for work. Under the Danish law if the employee had received salary during periods of illness for a total period of 120 days during any period of 12 consecutive months the employee will be dismissed immediately on the expiry of the 120 days of illness and while the employee is still ill.

The trade union HK, acting on behalf of the two applicants in the main proceedings, brought proceedings against their employers seeking compensation on the basis of the Anti-Discrimination Law. HK submitted that *both employees were suffering from a disability and that their employers were required to offer them reduced working hours, by virtue of the obligation to provide accommodation pursuant to Article 5 of Directive 2000/78*. HK also argued that *the Danish national law couldn't not be applied to those two employees, because their absences because of illness were the result of their disability*.⁹

The employers disputed that the applicants' state of health is covered by the concept of disability since the only incapacity that affected them was that they are not able to work

⁹ Joined Cases C-335/11 and 337/11 *Ring and Skuboe Werge* [2013] para. 23.

full-time. They also disputed that reduced working hours would constitute reasonable accommodation under the Directive.

Questions which were referred to the CJEU were as follows:

Is any person who, because of physical, mental or psychological impairments, cannot or can only to a limited extent carry out his work in a period that satisfies the requirement as to duration specified in Paragraph 45 of the judgment [in *Chacón Navas*] covered by the concept of disability within the meaning of [Directive 2000/78]?

This question in essence asked the court to (re)define disability. In 2006 the then European court of Justice made a judgement in a similar case of a woman who was certified as unfit for work on grounds of sickness and was not in a position to return to work in the short term. She was, according to the referring court, dismissed solely on account of the fact that she was absent from work because of sickness. (Case C13/05, *Chacon Navas v Eures Colectividades SA*).

In the judgment in this case which was adopted prior to the EU ascending to the UN CRPD the Court said: *Directive 2000/78 aims to combat certain types of discrimination as regards employment and occupation. In that context, the concept of 'disability' must be understood as referring to a limitation which results in particular from physical, mental or psychological impairments and which hinders the participation of the person concerned in professional life.*¹⁰ In this definition disability resides solely in the individual and for an impairment to reach the level of disability it has to hinder the participation, in this case, in professional life. There is no mention of the barriers in the environment. Following this definition the ECJ in 2006 reached a decision that *a person who has been dismissed by his employer solely on account of sickness does not fall within the general framework laid down for combating discrimination on grounds of disability by Directive 2000/78.*¹¹

UN CRPD AND EU LAW

Since this definition of disability the European Union acceded to the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities. The Convention was ratified by the decision of 26 November 2009. When (re)defining the concept of disability in the joint cases **Ring and Skouboe Werge** the CJEU explicitly defined the position of the UN CRPD as an international legal instrument in the EU law by stating that by approving the UN Convention the provisions of the Convention became an integral part of the European Union legal order. This means that EU legislation (Directive 2000/78) must be interpreted in a

¹⁰ Case C-13/15 *Cachon Navas* [2006] para. 43.

¹¹ *Chacon Navas* (52)

manner that is consistent with the CRPD. Furthermore, *by virtue of Article 216(2) Treaty on the Functioning of the EU, where international agreements are concluded by the European Union they are binding on its institutions, prevail over acts of the EU.*¹²

That is why the CJEU in its judgement in the joint cases C335/11 and C337/11 Ring and Skouboe Werge v Dansk Arbejdsgiverforening from 2013 redefined disability to bring it in line with the UN CRPD and reached a different judgement to the one in a similar case from 2006. In Ring and Skouboe Werge case the court ruled that a long term inability to participate in professional life is disability irrespective of the cause of such inability (sickness or an accident). *It must therefore be concluded that if a curable or incurable illness entails a limitation which results in particular from physical, mental or psychological impairments which in interaction with various barriers may hinder the full and effective participation of the person concerned in professional life on an equal basis with other workers, and the limitation is a long-term one, such an illness can be covered by the concept of 'disability' within the meaning of Directive 2000/78.*

On the other hand, an illness not entailing such a limitation is not covered by the concept of 'discrimination' within the meaning of Directive 2000/78.¹³

*A disability does not necessarily imply complete exclusion from work or professional life.*¹⁴

The person does not have to be considered a person with disability in a general sense or have substantial limitation in other activities of daily living outside professional life. The fact that an impairment in interaction with the environment caused limited or hindered participation of these two women in professional life makes them persons with disabilities in the context of work. The fact that inability to participate might have been mitigated by an action of employers created an obligation for them to take such an action. In these two cases such an action would be enabling workers to work part time in line with their remaining capacity. Such measure was not considered nor offered to the workers. In response to the question of whether the absence of workers was due to the fact that the employer has not implemented the measures appropriate in the specific situation to enable a person with a disability to perform his work the court ruled that such an action constituted denial of reasonable accommodation and thus discrimination on the ground of disability. *The circumstance that an employer has failed to take those measures may have the consequence, having regard to the obligation under Article 5 of Directive 2000/78, that the absences of a worker with a disability are attributable to the employer's failure to act, not to the worker's disability.*¹⁵

¹² Ring and Skouboe Werge (28)

¹³ Ring and Skouboe Werge (41)

¹⁴ Ring and Skouboe Werge (43)

¹⁵ Ring and Skouboe Werge (66)

This statement marks the shift the court made from the medical model of disability in the case *Chacon Navas* to the social model which sees the absence of workers, that is limitation in their participation not as one inherent in their impairment but rather a barrier in the environment (the employer's failure to act). In other words, the employer failed to provide reasonable accommodation.

The Court explained that disability is a hindrance to the exercise of a professional activity and not just the complete impossibility of exercising it. The Court also noted a difference between sickness and disability which cannot be equated. Sickness becomes disability only when and if it limits a person's participation (in professional life).

The court explicitly said that a condition caused by a medically diagnosed incurable illness provided that it is long-term and leads to a permanent reduction in functional capacity constitutes disability. It noted that disability does not mean that a person will necessarily have a need for special aids or the like but means solely or essentially that the person concerned is not able to work full-time. This means that persons with such conditions are protected by Directive 2000/78.

The Court did, however, emphasise that the condition or the impairment has to be long term. The UN CRPD seems to have adopted the concept of reasonable accommodation from Americans with Disabilities Act of 1990. Although the practice in the US foresees the so called temporary disability and even applies provisions pertaining to persons with disabilities to pregnant women who are also entitled to reasonable accommodation during pregnancy, the EU law and even the CRPD insist that disability can only result from a long term condition. It is natural that during negotiations of the Convention the governments were eager to limit the number of people who would be a protected category after identifying themselves with the definition of disability. However, there are arguments that support recognising even short term limitations of participation as disability. Seeing even temporary states that limit a person's participation as a disability will not necessarily unduly inflate the numbers of claimants of disability benefits if we accept that there is no universal classification of disability and that a person can be classified as a person with disability in some environments and not in others. Accepting temporary limitation of participation as disability could also contribute to seeing disability as something that can be transient in nature respecting the fact that situations change and people recover and/or find new ways of performing activities or new activities which suit the way in which their abilities have changed. Or, even more importantly, that the environments change especially in the light of new technological advances which remove barriers.

A person does not have to be substantially limited in performing major life activities (to echo Americans with Disabilities Act) in order to be deemed a person with disability in work. That is, people can be limited in performing activities at work while their ability to perform other major life activities outside work can remain relatively intact. Furthermore,

the Americans with Disabilities Act lists working as one of the major life activities.¹⁶ Disability as a result of an interaction between an impairment and the environment depends on requirements posed by a particular environment so it is logical to assume that working environment may pose requirements in which an impairment will lead to disability, i.e. limitation in participation. It is interesting to note that the inability to work full time is a limitation and not a complete absence of working ability.

Legislators in the State of New Jersey quoted figures which support the need for introducing temporary disability benefits: *disabling sickness or accident occurs throughout the working population at one time or another and approximately 15 % of the number of people at work may be expected to suffer disabling illness of more than one week per year.*¹⁷ Bearing in mind that sick leave in American states is very limited compared to European countries, the legislators found that recognising temporary disability *benefits employers by reducing employee turnover and increasing worker productivity*¹⁸.

PART TIME WORK AS REASONABLE ACCOMMODATION

When it comes to what actually constitutes reasonable accommodation, in the joint cases **Ring and Skouboe Werge** the CJEU, the referring court asked the CJEU whether a reduction in working hours is among the measures covered by Article 5 of the Directive. The Court looked into provisions of Directive 2000/78 which in Recital 20 states the following:

*Appropriate measures should be provided, i.e. effective and practical measures to adapt the workplace to the disability, for example adapting premises and equipment, **patterns of working time**, the distribution of tasks or the provision of training or integration resources.*¹⁹

Further to that, the Court concluded that reduction in working hours is an organisational measure (pattern of working time) that makes it possible for the worker to continue employment in accordance with the objective of the Directive.²⁰

The Court also noted that the definition of appropriate measures is not exhaustive but rather exemplary since it is impossible to prescribe all the circumstances arising in life.

¹⁶ Americans with Disabilities Act, Sec. 12102, available at <http://www.ada.gov/pubs/adastatute08.htm#12102>, (accessed 18 April 2016).

¹⁷ Temporary Disability Benefits Law, 41:21-26, available a http://lwd.dol.state.nj.us/labor/forms_pdfs/tdi/Law.pdf, (accessed 18 April 2016).

¹⁸ Temporary Disability Benefits Law

¹⁹ Council Directive 2000/78/EC, (20)

²⁰ *Ring and Skouboe Werge*, (56)

DISPROPORTIONATE BURDEN

The Directive details some other considerations that should be taken into account when determining whether a particular measure exceeds the reasonableness requirement:

*(21) To determine whether the measures in question give rise to a disproportionate burden, account should be taken in particular of the financial and other costs entailed, the scale and financial resources of the organisation or undertaking and the possibility of obtaining public funding or any other assistance.*²¹

The Court ruled that it is for the national court to assess whether a reduction in working hours, as an accommodation measure, represents a disproportionate burden on the employers.

It is to be expected that such measures will cause additional costs and require additional resources. That is why the state will step in with subsidies and other incentives so that the obligation of employers to provide reasonable accommodation does not interfere with the legitimate goal of any business enterprise to make profit. In securing such funds the state will acknowledge that for any individual the right to work is empowering in more ways than just financial. Due to its contribution to human dignity the right to work has been listed as one of the basic human rights.²² Although there is a general perception that being spared of the obligation to work to provide for oneself and rely on social welfare is somehow having an easy way out, exercising their right to work is of particular importance for the sense of dignity and self-worth of persons with disabilities. In the same way as everybody else, it gives them a power to be a more active holders of other rights and active agents of their own lives. At the same time, the level of the expectation of society and all its systems that should support inclusion is very low frequently leading to low self-expectations. Recognising this value of work for persons with disabilities forces governments to direct funds not only into providing social welfare benefits but also to providing support for persons with disabilities on the open labour market as well as funding other necessary adjustments so that this does not pose an undue burden for the employer. Apart from enforcing human rights of persons with disabilities such approach to disability policy would make use now discarded potential of persons with disabilities and would in the be more cost effective.

Although part time work can have negative impact on workers, for some categories of workers it can make a difference between being gainfully employed and socially included in line with their capacities and being excluded from the open labour market with all financial and human consequences such social exclusion entails.

²¹ Council Directive 2000/78/EC, (21)

²² Universal Declaration of Human Rights, article 23. "Everyone has the right to work, to free choice of employment, to just and favourable conditions of work and to protection against unemployment." <http://www.un.org/en/universal-declaration-human-rights/index.html>, (accessed 18 April 2016).